

Experimental gasification of glycerol-impregnated eucalyptus biomass for hydrogen-rich syngas

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Gasification
Glycerol-impregnated
Eucalyptus biomass
Residual glycerol
Hydrogen-rich syngas

ABSTRACT

This study presents an experimental investigation of the gasification performance of eucalyptus biomass impregnated with residual glycerol for hydrogen-enriched syngas production. Eucalyptus–residual glycerol mixtures containing 0, 10, and 20 wt% glycerol were gasified in a semi-industrial-scale downdraft reactor (45 kWth) under controlled operating conditions. Physicochemical characterization revealed that glycerol incorporation significantly modified fuel properties, resulting in a substantial increase in volatile matter and heating value. The higher heating value of the mixtures increased by up to 38% compared to raw eucalyptus biomass. Gas chromatography analysis showed that glycerol addition strongly influenced syngas composition. The mixture containing 20 wt% glycerol exhibited the highest hydrogen concentration, corresponding to a 32.90% increase relative to non-impregnated biomass, with a maximum hydrogen content of 22.29% obtained at 811 °C. The results indicate that glycerol impregnation enhances hydrogen-forming reaction pathways, though it is accompanied by variations in energetic performance parameters. The findings demonstrate that residual glycerol, an abundant byproduct of the biodiesel industry, represents a viable additive for modifying biomass gasification behavior and promoting hydrogen-rich syngas production. This approach provides a promising pathway for industrial residue valorization, contributing to waste management, resource efficiency, and sustainable energy generation within the framework of circular bioeconomy strategies.

1. Introduction

The growing concern over environmental pollution, climate change, and energy security has driven the search for renewable and sustainable energy sources. In this context, thermochemical processes, particularly gasification, have received significant attention due to their environmental and operational advantages [1–3].

Hydrogen has emerged as a promising energy carrier because of its high energy density and substantial potential for decarbonization, enabling a low-carbon economy and thus being regarded as a clean energy vector [4,5]. The importance of developing new hydrogen

production routes is closely linked to sustainable development, allowing for green energy generation through gasification processes [6]. However, the environmental viability of hydrogen depends directly on the technological pathways employed in its production, making the exploration of processes based on renewable resources an essential action [7–10].

Biomass gasification has been widely recognized as an efficient and effective technology for the thermochemical conversion of lignocellulosic materials into syngas, enabling hydrogen production with a lower carbon footprint compared to conventional fossil-fuel-based routes [11, 12].

This article is part of a special issue entitled: SBP2025 published in Biomass and Bioenergy.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2026.109238>

Received 15 December 2025; Received in revised form 4 March 2026; Accepted 4 March 2026

Available online 14 March 2026

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From this perspective, gasification stands out due to its high feedstock flexibility, its ability to promote the energy valorization of residues, and its associated environmental benefits [13–15]. Studies addressing the application of biomass gasification for energy generation continue to increase every year, as this technology not only contributes to mitigating climate change-related challenges and reducing dependence on fossil fuels, but also provides an important contribution to the circular economy through waste valorization strategies [16–18].

Despite its advantages, biomass gasification still faces significant challenges, including the inherently low H/C ratio of biomass, limited carbon conversion efficiency, and tar formation. Consequently, recent studies have focused on process intensification strategies to improve syngas quality and enhance hydrogen production, such as co-gasification and the use of hybrid materials to overcome these thermodynamic limitations. For instance, Wang et al. [19] demonstrated that bifunctional Ni-CaO-CaZrO₃ materials can significantly increase hydrogen purity by coupling catalytic sites with in situ CO₂ capture, thereby shifting the reaction equilibrium. Similarly, the integration of industrial residues into the energy chain has gained prominence; Zhang et al. [20] recently developed low-cost hybrid catalyst-sorbents derived from steel slag, achieving a hydrogen purity of 74.57% through sorption-enhanced gasification.

Biomass plays a central role in renewable energy strategies due to its carbon-neutral nature, wide availability, and compatibility with thermochemical conversion technologies [21–23]. In the Brazilian context, eucalyptus is a fast-growing species that stands out as one of the most relevant biomass resources due to its extensive availability and high energy potential, being considered a promising feedstock for gasification processes [24,25].

The eucalyptus production chain generates large quantities of lignocellulosic waste, consisting of branch trimmings, leaves, bark, twigs, and pruning debris, originating from agro-industries that produce a large amount of organic solid waste, representing a significant energy potential that is often underutilized.

Among strategies for intensifying the gasification process, modifying the fuel's physicochemical properties through treatments or co-processing has demonstrated significant potential. The incorporation of carbon and hydrogen-rich industrial residues, such as glycerol — an abundant byproduct of biodiesel production — emerges as an attractive alternative feedstock for gasification, contributing to waste valorization and management while reducing biodiesel production costs. In Brazil, the increasing production of biodiesel has resulted in the large-scale generation of this residue, whose high availability poses environmental challenges but also creates opportunities for its energy recovery [26]. Therefore, the conversion of waste into energy can be achieved by integrating eucalyptus waste with residual glycerol [27,28].

Glycerol exhibits high thermal reactivity and a composition favorable to the formation of light gaseous species, which may directly influence reforming and water-gas shift reactions during gasification [29]. Despite the growing interest in glycerol energy valorization, studies involving biomass impregnated with residual glycerol remain limited, particularly under operating conditions approaching semi-industrial scale.

In this context, the gasification of eucalyptus biomass impregnated with residual glycerol not only increases the heating value of the mixture but also modifies relevant physicochemical properties of the fuel, contributing to sustainable waste management and diversification of the energy matrix. Furthermore, it represents a promising alternative for energy and syngas production by combining lignocellulosic biomass utilization with the energy valorization of residues. This strategy may contribute both to improving syngas quality and to reducing environmental impacts associated with residual glycerol disposal [30].

The impregnation treatment of eucalyptus biomass using residual glycerol represents a promising approach from both energetic and environmental perspectives, integrating lignocellulosic biomass utilization with industrial waste valorization. However, the combined effect

of glycerol impregnation and key operational parameters - such as temperature and equivalence ratio - on gasification performance and hydrogen production remains insufficiently understood.

Beyond material development, understanding molecular-scale interactions between different feedstocks is crucial for maximizing process efficiency. In co-gasification systems, the presence of hydrogen-rich co-reactants may play a regulatory role. According to Cui et al. [31], reactive co-solvents can release polar aliphatic radicals that induce cleavage, oxidation, and amination of the biomass carbon skeleton, thereby promoting deep deoxygenation.

Moreover, studies coupling ReaxFF molecular dynamics with Density Functional Theory (DFT) have suggested that co-gasification synergy is often driven by free radical interactions. Cui et al. [32] reported that hydrogen donors can act as a source of •H radicals that suppress secondary tar condensation and favor hydrogen formation pathways. These findings suggest that hydrogen-rich additives, such as residual glycerol, may actively influence radical-mediated pathways during gasification, reinforcing the relevance of glycerol-based modifications.

Although laboratory-scale studies have explored the synergy between eucalyptus and residual glycerol, a significant gap remains in data derived from larger, engineering-relevant systems. Given these gaps, the primary objective of this work was to investigate the performance of eucalyptus biomass gasification impregnated with different proportions of residual glycerol in a semi-industrial-scale gasifier. The study evaluated the influence of key operational parameters on process performance and syngas composition, with emphasis on hydrogen-enriched syngas production under a waste valorization approach.

2. Methodology

The gasification process was investigated through semi-industrial-scale experiments. The eucalyptus biomass was impregnated with different proportions of residual glycerol, 0%, 10% and 20% by weight (called EGO, EG10, and EG20, respectively). The objective was to evaluate the influence of residual glycerol concentration on the generation and composition of syngas during the gasification process. The eucalyptus biomass without glycerol addition was also included in the experiments (designated EGO).

2.1. Pre-treatment of samples

The raw materials used in the experiments consisted of cylindrical eucalyptus chips with an average diameter of approximately 5 cm ± 1 cm, obtained from branch trimmings and pruning waste from agro-industries. The chip exhibited non-uniform dimensions and was used without prior grinding or size reduction. Residual glycerol was obtained from the biodiesel pilot plant of the Energy and Gas Laboratory (LEN), produced from waste frying oil (WFO) collected from commercial establishments in Salvador, Brazil, in liquid state (without going through refining and/or cleaning processes) [33].

All eucalyptus biomass samples were stored at the same location prior to impregnation with crude glycerol to standardize the characteristics of this raw material.

The mass of eucalyptus biomass and residual glycerol was measured in separate containers using a scale, then mixed in a hermetically sealed plastic drum after each raw material was added, with the drum manually stirred. Each mixture remained in the drum for 3 days (without stirring) to maximize the impregnation of residual glycerol into the eucalyptus and ensure that all added liquid glycerol was absorbed and evenly distributed throughout the eucalyptus chips. Mass losses during impregnation were considered negligible (<1%), based on repeated weighing.

To ensure the absorption of residual glycerol and control humidity, the mixtures (EGO, EG10 and EG20) were then arranged for a period of 7 days, in an elevated place about 1m from the ground (resembling a table), exposed to ambient air, but in a covered environment to

minimize the effects of bad weather, as illustrated in Fig. 1. After this period, each mixture was placed again in a plastic drum for weighing on a scale. A mixture of eucalyptus biomass impregnated with residual glycerol (still in cylindrical chips) was manually directed into the gasifier. Then, samples from each mixture were collected to determine the average moisture content before carbonation.

2.2. Samples characterization

The physicochemical characterization of the mixtures to be carbonated was performed by immediate analysis to evaluate their energy potential. Samples of each mixture (EG0, EG10, and EG20) were crushed in a knife mill (Usifer brand, model 310E) to determine the content of volatiles, carbon, and ash, as well as the higher heating value. The moisture content was determined for each mixture in chip form.

The moisture (M), ash (A), and volatile matter (V) contents of the samples were determined according to the respective standards ASTM E1756-08 (Standard Test Method for determination of Total Solids in Biomass), ASTM E1755-01 (Standard Test Method for Ash in Biomass), and ASTM D 5832-98 (Standard Test Method for volatile matter content of Activated Carbon Samples).

For the determination of M, A, and V, a muffle furnace (QUIMIS brand, model Q-318M24) was used with each sample of approximately $1\text{g} \pm 0.0003\text{g}$ mass for ash and volatile matter, heated to the respective temperatures and times: ash, $575\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h; volatiles, $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 7 min; as for moisture, the chips from each mixture were dried in an oven (FANEM brand, model S15 SE) at a temperature of $105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for a period of 24 h. The fixed carbon content (FC) was then determined indirectly using Equation (1).

$$\text{FC} = 100 - \text{V} - \text{A} \quad (1)$$

The chemical composition of eucalyptus biomass was defined based on elemental analysis data reported in the literature, considering studies involving similar eucalyptus species [34]. The adopted values fall within the compositional range typically reported for eucalyptus biomass, thereby ensuring representativeness and supporting the discussion presented in this work [35].

The glycerol used in this study was residual glycerol obtained as a byproduct of biodiesel production. As detailed elemental characterization was not performed, the elemental analysis was estimated assuming the residual glycerol was pure glycerol ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$). The elemental theoretical analysis was calculated based on the stoichiometric relationship derived from its molecular formula, as shown in Equation (2).

$$w_{i,\text{glyc}} = \frac{n_{i,\text{glyc}}}{n_{\text{glyc}}} \quad (2)$$

where: $w_{i,\text{glyc}}$ is the mass fraction of the element “i” in glycerol ($\text{kg}_{\text{carbon}}/\text{kg}_{\text{glyc}}$); $n_{i,\text{glyc}}$ is the number of moles of the element “i” in glycerol; n_{glyc} is the number of moles of glycerol.

Although residual glycerol may contain impurities such as water, methanol, inorganic salts, and residual fatty acids, it can be approximated as pure glycerol in thermochemical studies when a detailed compositional analysis is not available. The carbon content reported in the literature for residual glycerol can reach 58 wt%, reflecting the presence of residual organic compounds [27,36,37]. The values adopted here are consistent with data from the literature [30,38].

The elemental analysis of eucalyptus biomass and glycerol is available in Table 1. The chemical characterization of the biomass (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin content) was obtained from data reported in the literature for the same species as the present study [39–41], Table 2. These compositional ranges are consistent with the characteristics of eucalyptus biomass and were used to strengthen the discussion of the thermochemical results and product distribution obtained in this work.

The higher heating value (HHV), in MJ/kg, of the mixtures of fresh eucalyptus with glycerol was determined according to ASTM D2015 – 00 (Standard Test Method for Gross Calorific Value of Coal and Coke by the Adiabatic Bomb Calorimeter), in a calorimetric pump (IKA brand, model C2000 Basic). And the lower heating value (LHV), in MJ/kg, of the mixtures of eucalyptus with glycerol was calculated considering the total fraction of hydrogen in the mixture (eucalyptus + glycerol), obtained from the elemental chemical composition, through Equation (3) [42].

$$\text{LHV} = \text{HHV} - h_g(9 \times \text{H} + \text{M}) \quad (3)$$

where: LHV is lower heating value (MJ/kg); HHV is higher heating value (MJ/kg); h_g is latent heat of vaporization of water (≈ 2.260 MJ/kg); H is the total fraction of hydrogen in the fuel (%); M is the moisture content (%).

Table 1
Elemental analysis of eucalyptus biomass and glycerol.

Elemental analysis	Eucalyptus composition (wt %) ^a	Glycerol Composition (wt %) ^b
Carbon (C)	44.48 ± 0.035	39.13
Hydrogen (H)	6.04 ± 0.09	8.70
Oxygen (O)	49.35 ± 0.245	52.17
Nitrogen (N)	1.13 ± 0.12	-

^a The data are expressed as a percentage by weight, \pm standard deviation.

^b estimated using the molecular formula of glycerol.

Fig. 1. Preparation of eucalyptus biomass impregnated with glycerol for gasification.

Table 2
Structural composition of eucalyptus biomass reported in the literature.

Feedstocks	Carbohydrate composition (dry wt%)			Ref.
	Cellulose	Hemicellulose	Lignin	
Eucalyptus	40-51	10-18	20-30	[39–41]

2.3. Gasification process

The gasification experiments were carried out in a fixed-bed down-draft gasification plant operating at a semi-industrial scale, with a capacity of 45 kWth. This system consists of a fixed-bed reactor as its main component, with a concurrent reactor in a double-stage configuration (Termoquip Energia Alternativa Ltda), located at the Energy and Gas Laboratory (LEN) of the Polytechnic School of UFBA, in Salvador/Bahia. Fig. 2 shows the semi-industrial scale pilot gasification plant, and Fig. 3 illustrates the gasifier used. Mixtures of eucalyptus biomass and glycerol were gasified to evaluate the composition of the resulting syngas.

The mass of the mixture to be gasified was determined using a scale before it was fed into the aerator. The gasification plant operates in batch mode, and the mixture to be gasified (in the form of cylindrical chips, without going through a grinding process) is fed into the biomass inlet, in the upper part of the gasifier (silo), all at once, being carried out manually until the entire mixture is inserted into the silo. After the gasifier feeding process, the top cover was closed and then the gasification agent was supplied to initiate gasification.

The gasification agent used in the experiments was air, which was supplied through a nozzle in a radial direction and oriented to the center of the gasifier, with the inserted air being initially directed to the first heat exchanger (heat exchanger 1) before being fed into the gasifier zone.

At the beginning of each experiment, immediately after starting the air supply, the atmospheric air control valves on the orifice plates (upper and lower) were adjusted to promote temperature increase and initial combustion. Throughout the experiments, the two vibrators of the gasifier (upper and lower) were activated, according to the timer programming, in order to confirm that all the biomass inserted in the gasifier descended and was consumed throughout the gasification process and that the ashes that were on the grate were released and could be collected in the ashtray at the end of the experiment along with

unconverted char residues.

The differential pressures (upper and lower) and the temperature were the operational parameters monitored throughout the gasification experiments; instrumental accuracy was considered: thermocouples (± 1 °C) and differential pressure readings (± 0.05 cmH₂O).

The gasifier has two orifice plates (upper and lower), one for each reactor stage (first stage, or upper stage, and second stage, or lower stage). The upper and lower orifice plates have diameters equal to 0.01201 m and 0.01516 m, respectively. The air flow was regulated through control valves, one for each stage of gasification, and was evaluated by orifice plates, where the control of the gas valves occurred immediately after finishing the air supply to the gasifier and throughout the experiment, to observe the reduction in air flow, and thus guarantee the complete gasification of the mixture and temperature control.

Differential pressure was measured by reading the pressure difference in each U-gauge connected to the orifice plate, in cmH₂O. Temperature control was achieved at several points in the gasifier using K-type thermocouples connected to digital thermometers, allowing temperature measurement throughout the experiments. Thus, it was possible to observe the temperature in each zone of the gasification process: drying and pyrolysis (first stage), oxidation and reduction (second stage). After the syngas left the gasifier, temperatures were not recorded. Temperature and differential pressure data were collected manually every 10 min throughout the entire gasification process, from the beginning of air supply to the end, when the gasifier was turned off.

In the gasifier, the mixture went through the drying, pyrolysis, oxidation and reduction sections, for subsequent generation of the gaseous product. At the top of the gasifier, the drying zone removed moisture from the mixture of eucalyptus biomass and glycerol. Then, the beginning of decomposition and consequent devolatilization of the organic compounds present in the mixture, in addition to the generation of gases, liquid and char, occurred at the pyrolysis zone. In the next stage, where air is injected, the oxidation zone partially burns the coal and volatiles with a large release of energy, for consequent conversion of the coal into fuel gas, inside the reduction zone. The syngas generated in the gasifier went through three main sections: the first section carried out the removal of heavy particulates, utilizing cyclonic separation, the second section consisted of a catalytic reform to convert the tar and also the cooling of the gas via two shell and tube heat exchangers, the latter being heat exchanger with water as refrigerant (heat exchanger 2), and, finally, the third section filtered the gas in a bag filter with storage in a

Fig. 2. Semi-industrial scale pilot gasification plant.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the co-current fixed-bed downdraft gasifier.

gasholder sealed with water (lung) to control gas pressure variations. The gas generated throughout the process was directed at the two gas burners (flare), thus preventing its release into the atmosphere.

Throughout the gasification experiment, the equivalence ratio (ER) was evaluated, as it is the factor that will define the gasification performance, that is, the proportion of fuel burned due to complete combustion in relation to the amount gasified, thus establishing the composition of the gas generated and its heating value [43]. The air supply flow rate varied during the experiment and was maintained for a minimum of 20 min to analyze the gas composition.

The gaseous product obtained from the gasification process was collected shortly after it passed through the lung vessel, at the bottom of the process, in a gas storage bag, coupled with a filter containing two layers of cotton interspersed with a layer of calcium chloride (to remove possible particulates still present in the gaseous sample). The other products generated in the gasification experiment, liquid (tar) and solid (ash), were collected at the end of the process for quantification but were

not analyzed in relation to their composition.

The gasification process was completed, and the gasifier was turned off when gas production ended, as observed when it was no longer possible to sustain flare flames.

Due to the batch nature of the experiments, fluctuations in temperature and gas composition were observed. Such variations are characteristic of batch gasification systems and are associated with progressive fuel conversion, changes in reaction zones, and evolving oxidant-to-fuel ratios.

The verification of the gasification process performance in this study was carried out by calculating the gas calorific value, determining the syngas composition, and estimating the carbon conversion efficiency (CCE) and the cold gas efficiency (CGE), which are parameters used to evaluate gasification performance.

2.4. Syngas analysis

The composition of the gaseous product collected during the gasification experiments in a gas storage bag was analyzed by gas chromatography using a GC (Thermo Scientific, model Trace 1610). The focus of the syngas obtained was only for the concentrations of H₂, CO, CO₂ and CH₄.

The lower heating value of the syngas (LHV_g) was calculated considering only the percentage of combustible gases present in the syngas (H₂, CO and CH₄), obtained using gas chromatography, through Equation (4) [36].

$$LHV_g = 0.12622.P_{CO} + 0.10788.P_{H_2} + 0.35814.P_{CH_4} \quad (4)$$

where: LHV_g - lower heating value of the syngas (MJ/Nm³); P_{CO} - fraction of CO present in syngas; P_{H_2} - is fraction of H₂ present in syngas; P_{CH_4} - fraction of CH₄ present in syngas.

2.5. Equivalence ratio (ER)

The equivalence ratio (ER) is defined as the ratio of the actual mass flow rate of air to the stoichiometric mass flow rate of air required for complete combustion. The equivalence ratio (ER) was calculated using Equation (5) [42]. ER values correspond to time-averaged air flow rates during steady-state operation.

$$ER = \frac{\dot{m}_{air,real}}{\dot{m}_{air,est}} = \frac{R_{(A/C)real}}{R_{(A/C)est}} \quad (5)$$

where: $\dot{m}_{air,real}$ is the actual air mass flow rate (kg/h); $\dot{m}_{air,est}$ the stoichiometric air mass flow rate (kg/h); $R_{(A/C)real}$ the actual air/fuel ratio (dimensionless); $R_{(A/C)est}$ the stoichiometric air/fuel ratio (dimensionless).

The air mass flow rate was determined in accordance with the ABNT NBR ISO standard. 5167-1:2022 [44]. Considering that the fuel was a mixture of eucalyptus biomass and glycerol, it was necessary to determine the mass fractions of the elements in the mixture, Equations (6)–(8).

$$w_{C,mix} = f_{glyc} \times w_{C,glyc} + (1 - f_{glyc}) \times w_{C,euc} \quad (6)$$

$$w_{H,mix} = f_{glyc} \times w_{H,glyc} + (1 - f_{glyc}) \times w_{H,euc} \quad (7)$$

$$w_{O,mix} = f_{glyc} \times w_{O,glyc} + (1 - f_{glyc}) \times w_{O,euc} \quad (8)$$

where: $w_{C,mix}$ - mass fraction of carbon in the mixture (kg_{carbon}/kg_{fuel}); $w_{H,mix}$ - mass fraction of hydrogen in the mixture ($kg_{hydrogen}/kg_{fuel}$); $w_{O,mix}$ - mass fraction of oxygen in the mixture (kg_{oxygen}/kg_{fuel}); f_{glyc} - mass fraction of glycerol in the mixture (%); f_{euc} - mass fraction of eucalyptus in the mixture, ($f_{euc} = 1 - f_{glyc}$), (%).

Converting to mass of oxygen per kilogram of fuel, using Equation (9).

$$m_{O_2,est} = (2.667 \times w_{C,mix} + 8 \times w_{H,mix} - w_{O,mix}) \quad (9)$$

where: $m_{O_2,est}$ - mass of oxygen per kilogram of fuel (kg_{O_2}/kg_{comb})

To convert and calculate stoichiometric oxygen in stoichiometric air, since the fluid was air, it was assumed that the mass fraction of oxygen in air is approximately 21%, as per Equation (10).

$$m_{air,est} = \frac{m_{O_2,est}}{0.21} \quad (10)$$

where: $m_{air,est}$ - mass of air per kilogram of fuel (kg_{air}/kg_{comb})

The gasification experiments were carried out by varying the flow rate of the gasification agent, in order to evaluate the behavior of the gas obtained in this process.

2.6. Gasification efficiencies

The carbon balance was established to quantify the distribution of carbon among the gas, char, and tar phases produced during gasification. The carbon conversion efficiency (CCE) is defined as the fraction of biomass carbon converted into the components of syngas, and was evaluated based on the carbon balance and the carbon distribution in the gaseous products, normalized [38,45]. The molar amounts of the major carbon-containing species (CO, CO₂, and CH₄) were obtained from the measured syngas composition using stoichiometric conversions. The fraction of carbon converted into the gas phase was calculated from the molar gas composition determined by gas chromatography (GC). The mass of carbon in the feed mixture into the gasifier was calculated from the mass of fuel mixture supplied and its carbon mass fraction (calculated from the elemental analysis of the fuel mixture). The mass of carbon converted into gaseous products was determined by subtracting the mass of carbon retained in the solid char and the mass of the tar fraction, as expressed in Equation (11). Carbon contained in residues (char and tar) was estimated assuming fixed carbon fractions of 75% for char and 70% for tar, consistent with values reported in the literature [46].

$$m_{C,gas} = m_{C,mix} - m_{C,char} - m_{C,tar} \quad (11)$$

where: $m_{C,mix}$ - mass of carbon in the feed mixture (kg); $m_{C,char}$ - mass of carbon in char (kg); $m_{C,tar}$ - mass of carbon in tar (kg); $m_{C,gas}$ - mass of carbon converted into gaseous products (kg)

The carbon conversion efficiency was calculated as the ratio between the mass of the carbon converted in gaseous products and the mass of carbon in the feed mixture into the gasifier, Equation (12) [38,45].

$$CCE(\%) = \frac{m_{C,gas}}{m_{C,mix}} \times 100 \quad (12)$$

where: $m_{C,gas}$ - mass of carbon converted into gaseous products (kg); $m_{C,mix}$ - mass of carbon in the feed mixture (kg)

The cold gas efficiency (CGE) was calculated to assess the overall energy conversion efficiency of the gasification process, and is defined as the fraction of chemical energy contained in product gas over the total energy of biomass [45]. The CGE was determined using the lower heating values (LHV) of the syngas and the fuel mixture, as given by Equation (13) [45].

$$CGE(\%) = \frac{LHV_g \times V_{gas}}{LHV \times m_{mix}} \times 100 \quad (13)$$

where: LHV_g - lower heating value of syngas (MJ/Nm^3); V_{gas} - the estimated gas volume (Nm^3); LHV - lower heating value of the fuel mixture (MJ/kg); m_{mix} - mass of the fuel mixture fed (kg)

The adopted methodology allows consistent estimation of gas yield and process efficiencies even in the absence of direct gas flow rate measurements, relying on a carbon balance approach applied in gasification studies [38,45].

Product yields, tar and char, were calculated with Equation (14) [27].

$$Y(\%) = \frac{m_{res}}{m_{mix}} \times 100 \quad (14)$$

where: m_{res} - the mass of the residues (tar or char) (kg); m_{mix} - the mass of the mixture (kg)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sample characterization

Table 3 summarizes the results of the proximate analysis tests and the heating values of the eucalyptus biomass and glycerol mixtures. The

Table 3

Results of the tests of immediate analysis and heating value of eucalyptus mixtures with glycerol.

Immediate analysis (wt%)			
	Glycerol Ratio (wt%)		
	0 (EG0)	10 (EG10)	20 (EG20)
Moisture (M)	21.00	18.39	19.52
Ash (A)	1.28	2.22	2.54
Volatile (V)	51.10	72.80	74.87
Fixed Carbon (FC)	15.38	11.37	6.86
Heating value (MJ/kg)			
HHV	13.35	18.09	18.37
LHV	11.51	16.25	16.45

progressive incorporation of glycerol altered the fuel's physicochemical properties, with direct implications for gasification behavior. The proximate analysis and heating values determinations were not based on multiple independent replicates.

The addition of glycerol resulted in a substantial increase in volatile matter, from 51.10 wt% (EG0) to 74.87 wt% (EG20), while fixed carbon decreased from 15.38 wt% to 6.86 wt%. This shift indicates a transition toward a volatilization-dominated conversion regime, favoring homogeneous gas-phase reactions during gasification [47]. Although ash content increased moderately with glycerol addition, it remained below levels associated with operational instability in fixed-bed downdraft gasifiers.

The moisture content of the EG10 and EG20 mixtures analyzed was below 20%, within the range recommended for gasification applications [48]. Elevated moisture content increases the energy required for drying, which slows ignition propagation and reduces gasifier efficiency [49]. The variations observed among the mixtures may be associated with the impregnation procedure and glycerol–biomass interactions, which can influence water retention behavior. Previous studies have indicated that glycerol impregnation may modify hydrophilic characteristics and promote partial glycerol leaching in the presence of moisture [50].

The higher heating value (HHV) increased from 13.35 (EG0) to 18.37 (EG20) MJ/kg, confirming the energetic upgrading effect of glycerol blending. This enhancement reflects the increased volatile fraction and altered elemental composition of the mixtures. Elemental analysis indicates higher H/C and O/C ratios in glycerol compared to eucalyptus biomass, which likely contributed to the observed increase in heating value in the mixtures EG10 and EG20. Similar behavior has been reported for glycerol-treated biomass systems [51].

Fig. 4 shows the variation in the higher and lower heating values of the analyzed mixtures. The results confirm that glycerol addition significantly improves the fuel's energetic properties. Comparable trends

Fig. 4. Higher and lower heating value of eucalyptus mixtures with glycerol percentages.

have been reported in glycerol–biomass systems, including co-pyrolysis studies, where heating value improvements between 45% and 61% have been observed [30,41,52–54].

3.2. Gasification

3.2.1. Glycerol to biomass blending ratio

Table 4 presents the average syngas composition (mole percentage), gas lower heating value (LHVg), carbon conversion efficiency (CCE) and cold gas efficiency (CGE) for all studied mixtures. Considering that the combustible fraction of syngas is primarily composed of carbon monoxide (CO), hydrogen (H₂), and methane (CH₄), only these components were included in the LHVg calculation.

Fig. 5 illustrates the composition of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and methane in the syngas generated from the gasification of eucalyptus biomass impregnated with residual glycerol, using air as the gasification agent. All gasification experiments of the mixtures were performed in duplicate, and the error bars represent the standard deviation.

Hydrogen concentration increased significantly with glycerol addition, rising from 15.47 wt% (EG0) to 20.56 wt% (EG20), corresponding to a 32.90% increase relative to non-impregnation eucalyptus. This behavior indicates enhanced devolatilization, leading to the formation of oxygenated intermediates and the promotion of steam reforming reactions [55].

A reduction in CO mole fraction was observed with glycerol incorporation. The decrease in CO concentration (-25.91% relative to EG0), accompanied by an increase in CO₂, supports the predominance of the water–gas shift (WGS) reaction under glycerol-rich conditions. This shift is thermodynamically favored by the greater local availability of vapor from glycerol decomposition and elevated temperatures at the oxidation-reduction interface [56].

Despite the substantial hydrogen enhancement, the maximum concentrations remained below values reported for advanced catalytic systems. Wang et al. [19] demonstrated that bifunctional materials combining catalytic reforming activity with in situ CO₂ capture can overcome thermodynamic equilibrium limitations, yielding high-purity hydrogen streams. In the present study, the absence of a CO₂ sorption mechanism likely imposed equilibrium constraints, where CO₂ accumulation restricted further hydrogen enrichment. Consequently, although glycerol impregnation intensified hydrogen formation, thermodynamic limitations imposed by CO₂ presence determined the attainable hydrogen levels.

The hydrogen enhancement observed here may also be interpreted within broader framework of reaction intensification strategies. Modifications to the reaction environment have been widely recognized as effective approaches for improving hydrogen generation. Zhang et al. [20] reported that catalyst–sorber hybrid materials derived from steel slag enhanced hydrogen production by promoting reforming reactions and enabling in situ CO₂ capture.

Similarly, equilibrium limitations typical of thermochemical systems provide additional context. Sorption enhanced steam reforming (SESR) has demonstrated that hydrogen purity can be significantly improved through the combined effects of catalytic reforming and in situ CO₂ capture [19]. Wang et al. [19] showed that Ni–CaO–CaZrO₃ bifunctional materials enhanced hydrogen purity by promoting reforming reactions while simultaneously shifting reaction equilibria via CO₂ adsorption.

Studies on co-gasification in supercritical water (co-SCWG) involving lignocellulosic biomass were conducted by Cui et al. [31] indicated that the co-solvents such as N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) promote an increase in hydrogen fraction. This effect was attributed to synergistic radical-mediated interactions that facilitate bond cleavage and enhance hydrogen-forming pathways [31,32].

The gas lower heating value (LHVg) increased from 4.10 MJ·Nm⁻³ (EG0) to 4.38 MJ·Nm⁻³ (EG10), followed by a slight reduction to 4.18 MJ·Nm⁻³ (EG20). The increase observed for EG10 indicates an

Table 4

Result of the average composition, lower heating value of the gas produced, carbon conversion efficiency and cold gas efficiency for different proportions of residual glycerol in the mixture.

Gas Composition (%)	Glycerol Ratio (wt%)				
	0 (EG0)	10 (EG10)	20 (EG20)	Increase 0-10 (%)	Increase 0-20 (%)
H ₂	15.47 ± 3.50	19.00 ± 1.38	20.56 ± 1.85	22.82	32.90
CO	14.86 ± 1.63	14.19 ± 2.14	11.01 ± 1.30	-4.51	-25.91
CO ₂	12.57 ± 2.04	14.56 ± 1.49	17.03 ± 1.32	15.83	35.48
CH ₄	1.54 ± 0.33	1.49 ± 0.40	1.61 ± 0.13	-3.25	4.55
Gas lower heating value (MJ/Nm³)					
LHV _g	4.10 ± 0.68	4.38 ± 0.39	4.18 ± 0.30	6.82	1.95
Gasification efficiencies					
CCE (%)	91.94 ± 6.75	87.38 ± 2.26	89.58 ± 3.92	-4.96	-2.57
CGE (%)	31.43 ± 1.53	34.22 ± 6.21	24.53 ± 5.54	8.87	-21.96

Fig. 5. Effect of glycerol concentration on the composition of the gas generated in the gasification process.

improvement in syngas energetic quality associated with glycerol addition. The absence of a proportional increase at EG20 suggests a saturation effect, in which further glycerol incorporation no longer significantly increases the calorific value.

Fig. 6 summarizes the overall process performance indicators as a function of glycerol content in the fuel mixture. Conversion efficiency (CCE) remained consistently high for all conditions, indicating that glycerol addition did not significantly impair carbon conversion. Cold gas efficiency (CGE) exhibited a non-linear behavior, increasing for EG10 and decreasing markedly for EG20. This divergence reflects the balance between hydrogen enhancement and depletion of energetically favorable species such as CO.

The reduction in CGE at EG20 indicates that the overall energy conversion efficiency depends not only on the gas heating value but also on the gas yield and reaction selectivity. Increased CO₂ formation and higher tar yields (EG10) suggest partial redistribution of fuel energy

Fig. 6. Effect of glycerol content on gasification performance.

toward condensable hydrocarbons.

The data in **Table 5** were calculated as the ratio of the mass of the residues to the mass of the feed mixture. Tar formation increased substantially with glycerol addition while char yield decreased at higher glycerol ratios. These results indicate that glycerol incorporation predominantly influenced volatile generation rather than solid residue formation. The increased tar production suggests that volatile-driven tar formation pathways dominated over radical-mediated suppression mechanisms proposed in theoretical studies [32].

Despite increased tar formation, hydrogen production did not decrease proportionally, indicating that hydrogen-forming reactions were simultaneously enhanced. Similar selectivity trends have been reported in glycerol conversion studies [38].

The increase in hydrogen concentration with glycerol addition is consistent with literature findings [57], which attributes this behavior to higher effective H/C and O/C ratios. Conversely, increased CO₂ formation is associated with oxidation reactions promoted by air gasification.

Beyond compositional effects, the progressive hydrogen enhancement suggests the presence of synergistic chemical interactions. Cui et al. [31] reported that hydrogen-rich materials act as effective donors of reactive •H radicals, facilitating biomass fragmentation and promoting gas-phase reactions. Residual glycerol, due to its high hydrogen content and simpler molecular structure compared with lignocellulosic components, is likely to perform a similar function in the co-gasification system. The elevated hydrogen concentrations observed in EG10 and EG20 indicate that glycerol may enhance radical-mediated depolymerization and favor reforming pathways [31].

According to Wei et al. [36], the lower CO concentration in the gas when adding 20% glycerol may be due to the lower oxygen content in the mixture. Manara et al. [52] attributed CO behavior in glycerol-containing systems to catalytic cracking reactions, the Boudouard reaction, and the higher conversion of glycerol compared with biomass. Overall, incorporating residual glycerol into eucalyptus biomass increases the effective H/C ratio of the feedstock, enhancing fuel reactivity and favoring hydrogen-rich syngas production. These findings indicate that glycerol impregnation represents a promising strategy to mitigate intrinsic compositional limitations of eucalyptus biomass.

Higher glycerol ratios likely intensified secondary reactions and condensable hydrocarbon formation, reducing the fraction of chemical

Table 5
Product yields from gasification of eucalyptus mixtures with glycerol.

Products yields (%)	Glycerol Ratio (wt%)				
	0 (EG0)	10 (EG10)	20 (EG20)	Increase 0-10 (%)	Increase 0-20 (%)
Char	0.80 ± 0.27	0.89 ± 0.59	0.649 ± 0.53	11.25	-18.88
Tar	4.11 ± 1.47	6.97 ± 1.14	5.78 ± 1.86	69.59	40.63

energy effectively transferred to the gaseous phase. The negligible char formation observed at higher glycerol ratios indicates that carbon conversion remained efficient. Therefore, the reduction in CGE with the addition of glycerol appears to be primarily due to a redistribution of chemical energy toward condensable hydrocarbons rather than incomplete gasification. This behavior can be attributed to the altered devolatilization characteristics of the blended fuel, as glycerol because of its highly oxygenated structure and low thermal stability — undergoes rapid decomposition, generating a broad spectrum of condensable oxygenated intermediates [29].

The observed increase in tar production with glycerol addition suggests that the hydrogen-donor effect proposed in theoretical studies [32], may not have been dominant under the present experimental conditions. Although hydrogen-rich additives are frequently associated with radical-mediated tar suppression mechanisms, the impact of additives on tar evolution is strongly dependent on operating conditions, suggesting that radical-mediated suppression mechanisms may compete with enhanced volatile-driven tar formation pathways, since glycerol is also known to significantly improve volatile release during thermal decomposition. Unlike theoretical predictions, the present experimental results indicate that glycerol impregnation may promote tar formation, suggesting that process conditions play a decisive role in determining the dominant reaction pathways.

Therefore, when gassing eucalyptus impregnated with glycerol, it is possible to observe that it minimizes the amount of oxygen needed per kilogram of mixture, since glycerol has a higher mass fraction of oxygen compared to eucalyptus biomass. And the maximization in hydrogen generation when using eucalyptus mixtures containing residual glycerol can also be explained by the molecular composition of glycerol, which positively influences the reactivity of the gasification process by increasing volatile content and thus favoring reforming and gas-water displacement reactions.

3.2.2. Influence of gasification temperature

Figs. 7–9 illustrate the influence of temperature on syngas composition. Temperature strongly affected gas concentrations, favoring endothermic reactions.

For the EG0 mixture, a decrease in hydrogen generation was observed in the temperature range from 618 °C to 770 °C; when the temperature was raised by 20 °C, hydrogen generation increased, but at 813 °C, the hydrogen concentration decreased. Regarding CO, the highest percentage was observed at 700 °C, while CO₂ showed the lowest generation at 770 °C. This behavior may have been further influenced by the higher moisture content of EG0 (21.00 wt%), as part of the supplied energy is consumed for water evaporation, reducing the effective reaction temperature. The combined influence of ER and moisture-thermal effects explains the non-monotonic behavior of hydrogen. These results highlight the coupled sensitivity of temperature, ER, and moisture in governing syngas composition under practical gasification conditions.

For EG10, when varying the reaction temperature from 785 °C to 860 °C, an initial increase in the concentration of hydrogen was observed followed by a reduction in the temperature range between 810 and 834 °C, from where an expansion in hydrogen generation was observed, reaching a concentration of 21.47% at a temperature of 860 °C. The methane concentration showed a slight increase, with a maximum generation of 2.11% at 810 °C. The CO concentration reached its maximum at 810 °C. For CO₂, the lowest generation of this gas occurred at 834 °C and the maximum at 864 °C.

In EG20, varying the reaction temperature from 750 °C to 811 °C yielded a maximum hydrogen yield (22.98 wt%) at 811 °C. A slight variation in CH₄ concentration was observed, suggesting that high temperatures promoted endothermic reforming reactions, which consume CH₄ and thus increase H₂ [58]. The concentrations of CO₂ and CO showed the highest levels at 800 °C. In general, H₂, CO₂, and CO showed similar behavior with respect to the effect of concentration on temperature.

Fig. 7. Effect of temperature on production gas yield and mole fraction of the EG0: a) H₂; b) CO₂; c) CO; d) CH₄.

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on production gas yield and mole fraction of the EG10: a) H₂; b) CO₂; c) CO; d) CH₄.

Fig. 9. Effect of temperature on production gas yield and mole fraction of the EG20: a) H₂; b) CO₂; c) CO; d) CH₄.

The direct influence of temperature on the production of CO and H₂ in the biomass gasification process can be explained mainly by the

reactions that occur in the oxidation and reduction stages, caused by the interactions that occur between carbon and oxygen, during the

combustion reactions and the partial reaction of hydrogen; between carbon and carbon dioxide (Boudouard reaction), and between carbon and water vapor (gas-water displacement reaction) [59,60].

The temperature plays a fundamental role in defining the gasification reaction pathways. The values observed for EG10 (≈ 860 °C) and EG20 (≈ 811 °C) coincide with increased hydrogen levels, supporting the interpretation that thermal severity strongly influences hydrogen formation. This behavior is consistent with the temperature-driven reaction intensification mechanisms described by Alves et al. [38], who demonstrated that elevated temperatures enhance gas production by accelerating the cleavage of C–C and C–O bonds. Under such conditions, reforming reactions and the decomposition of oxygenated intermediates become thermodynamically and kinetically favored, thereby enhancing hydrogen generation [38]. Analogously, the increase in hydrogen concentration observed in the syngas with increasing gasification temperature in the current work suggests that similar thermally driven mechanisms are operative under gasification conditions.

Investigations on the co-supercritical water gasification of cellulose and polystyrene, carried out by Cui et al. [32], demonstrated that the temperature-dependent evolution of major hydrocarbon radicals plays a decisive role in governing reaction pathways and hydrogen formation, suggesting that increasing temperature intensifies radical generation and promotes interactions between hydrogen-rich and oxygenated fragments, facilitating bond cleavage and enhancing gas-phase reactions [32]. In co-gasification systems (such as eucalyptus + glycerol), hydrogen-rich materials can act as $\bullet\text{H}$ radical donors, and glycerol may promote the fragmentation of the biomass carbon framework. This effect can enhance reforming reactions and the water–gas shift reaction, contributing to the hydrogen peak observed at 811 °C.

Similar results were obtained by Skoulou et al. [27], when he observed that an increase in temperature ($T > 650$ °C) increases the concentration of CO but decreases the concentration of CO_2 . At the same time, that of hydrogen shows slight expansion, and at high temperature

($T > 850$ °C) there was a greater reduction in the concentration of CO_2 , which, according to the author, was due to the activation of the Boudouard reaction, and also to the vapor gasification reactions of glycerol and methane. Yao et al. [61] studied gasification with wood chips under different moisture contents and observed that when using the raw material, a large amount of energy was needed to perform its drying, thus affecting the composition of the products generated.

The effect of temperature on the gasification of biomass containing glycerol was studied by Sricharoenchaikul et al. [62], who obtained higher concentrations of hydrogen at a temperature of 900 °C, with an increase in the concentration of methane and CO at this temperature. Manara et al. [52] observed that when glycerol was added to the co-pyrolysis process, at 630 °C, the hydrogen and carbon monoxide fractions present in the obtained gas increased, CH_4 remained at the same level, while the CO_2 fraction decreased.

Thus, the optimum temperature of 811 °C was considered for the hydrogen to reach a maximum value, considering gasification with glycerol impregnation in a percentage of 20% of glycerol addition to the eucalyptus, EG20 mixture, with a maximum hydrogen generation value of 22.29%, while a generation of 19% was obtained for the mixture containing 10% of glycerol addition to the eucalyptus, at a temperature of 810 °C.

In addition to temperature, syngas composition is strongly influenced by the equivalence ratio (ER), which regulates oxygen supply to the reactor. Therefore, the subsequent analysis focuses on the role of ER in governing gasification behavior.

3.2.3. Influence of equivalence ratio (ER)

Figs. 10–12 present the effect of ER on syngas composition. For the EG0 mixture, it was possible to observe that varying the air equivalence ratio from 0.32 to 0.41 caused an initial increase in the generation of all gases obtained, and this increase was more accentuated for the generation of hydrogen, followed by a decrease in the mole fraction of the

Fig. 10. Influence of equivalence ratio on the syngas composition of a biomass EG0: a) H₂; b) CO₂; c) CO; d) CH₄.

Fig. 11. Influence of equivalence ratio on the syngas composition of a biomass EG10: a) H₂; b) CO₂; c) CO; d) CH₄.

Fig. 12. Influence of equivalence ratio on the syngas composition of a biomass EG20: a) H₂; b) CO₂; c) CO; d) CH₄.

gases generated, probably caused by excess oxygen. Thus, the results indicate that the optimal ER was 0.33 for generating 18.93% hydrogen

during eucalyptus gasification.

For the EG10 mixture, when the ER varies from 0.27 to 0.44, the H₂ concentration underwent an initial increase, followed by a decrease as the ER increased, with the highest concentration of hydrogen for ER being 0.28; the lowest CO₂ concentrations were in the ER range of 0.29 to 0.34; the composition of CH₄ showed a succinct variation when increasing the ER. The maximum hydrogen concentration, 21.47%, was obtained with an ER of 0.28.

In the EG20 mixture, the concentrations of H₂, CO, and CO₂ increased with ER from 0.21 to 0.37, reaching the highest hydrogen concentration at ER = 0.35 (22.29%). The CH₄ concentration was not affected by changing the ER from 0.21 to 0.37. Similar results were obtained by Skoulou et al. [27] when gassing lignocellulosic biomass with 49% by weight glycerol, the best yield of gaseous products was obtained at 850 °C and an ER of 0.4. Also, according to Skoulou et al. [27], the increase in temperature and the equivalence ratio improve yields. Wei et al. [36] observed that when varying the ER from 0 to 0.3, it obtained a higher conversion into CO₂, CO and H₂. Still, when the ER was increased further due to combustion reactions, it resulted in lower concentrations of CO and H₂.

The results indicate that the optimal equivalence ratio varied across the studied mixtures, indicating a strong dependence on fuel composition. While EG10 exhibited maximum hydrogen concentration at a comparatively lower ER (0.28), EG20 required a higher ER (0.35) to achieve peak hydrogen production. This behavior suggests that glycerol incorporation modifies the effective oxygen balance and reaction regime of the system.

At moderate glycerol addition (EG10), the increased volatile content and the highly oxygenated structure of glycerol likely enhanced the formation of reactive intermediates, allowing efficient oxidation–reduction coupling at lower external oxygen supply. In contrast, at higher glycerol ratios (EG20), the substantial increase in volatile release may intensify endothermic decomposition and reforming reactions, thereby increasing the system's thermal demand. Under such conditions, higher ER values become necessary to sustain reaction temperatures and maintain favorable gas-phase conversion pathways.

Hydrogen concentration exhibited characteristic maxima at intermediate ER values. These results confirm that ER acts as a thermo-reactive control parameter governing oxidation intensity and reaction pathways [54].

Although glycerol addition influenced syngas composition, variations in equivalence ratio (ER) also played a significant role. The observed dispersion of ER values across experimental runs likely contributed to fluctuations in gas composition, particularly affecting the balance between CO and CO₂ formation. This behavior is consistent with thermochemical expectations, where ER governs the extent of oxidation and secondary gas-phase reactions.

Despite ER fluctuations, hydrogen concentration consistently increased with glycerol addition, indicating a dominant chemical effect associated with the additive.

A detailed techno-economic feasibility analysis was not within the scope of the present investigation, which primarily focused on the thermochemical behavior and gas composition. Nevertheless, a preliminary economic perspective can be reasonably considered based on the intrinsic characteristics of the modified fuel. Residual glycerol, a low-value by-product of the biodiesel industry, is significantly cheaper than conventional biomass feedstocks. Therefore, its incorporation into the fuel matrix reduces the overall raw-material cost. Additionally, the observed increase in the higher heating value, reaching up to 38% relative to pure eucalyptus biomass, indicates a substantial improvement in the energetic quality of the feedstock. From a process standpoint, fuels with higher HHV generally favor enhanced thermal efficiency and improved reactor performance. Consequently, although a formal economic assessment was not performed, the simultaneous reduction in feedstock costs and increase in energy density suggest that glycerol-impregnated biomass may offer greater economic

attractiveness than conventional biomass gasification systems.

4. Conclusions

The present study investigated the effect of residual glycerol impregnation on the gasification performance of eucalyptus biomass, with particular emphasis on hydrogen-rich syngas production.

The highest hydrogen concentration was obtained for the mixture containing 20 wt% glycerol, corresponding to a 32.90% increase relative to non-impregnated eucalyptus. This behavior indicates that glycerol addition enhances volatile-driven reaction mechanisms and promotes hydrogen-forming pathways during gasification. However, the improvement in hydrogen yield was accompanied by reductions in cold gas efficiency and slight variations in carbon conversion efficiency, highlighting the inherent trade-offs between gas composition and energetic performance.

The results further demonstrated that residual glycerol affects both chemical and thermal aspects of the gasification process. Although hydrogen formation was intensified, the observed modifications in reactor temperature profiles at higher glycerol ratios likely contributed to increased tar formation and partial energetic penalties. These findings emphasize the complex interaction between fuel composition, reaction selectivity, and thermal behavior in co-gasification systems.

From a broader perspective, residual glycerol emerges as a promising, low-cost, renewable additive for thermochemical conversion processes. Its utilization in biomass gasification provides a viable pathway for industrial residue valorization, contributing simultaneously to waste management, resource efficiency, and hydrogen-rich syngas production. This strategy aligns with circular economy principles by integrating biodiesel byproducts into bioenergy conversion pathways, supporting sustainable energy generation and diversifying the renewable energy matrix.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniela Araújo Costa: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marcos Fábio de Jesus:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Felipe Lima de Araújo:** Investigation. **Felipe Andrade Torres:** Writing – review & editing. **Delano Mendes de Santana:** Visualization, Project administration. **Silvio A.B.V. de Melo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Francisco Jarmeson Silva Bandeira:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Ednildo Andrade Torres:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support provided by the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado da Bahia (FAPESB), through the INCITERE program (PIE 0008/2022), and the Federal University of Bahia (UFBA) for their institutional and academic contributions. We also extend our sincere thanks to the Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) and the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) for their financial support and commitment to fostering research and education in Brazil.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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